

A CRITICAL SURVEY ON NEW TRENDS IN AMAZON

Krushita Desai

Research scholar,

Mumbai University, Mumbai.

Abstract:

The arrival of second wave of covid-19 is more harmful as compare to first way. Every individual had come out of the trauma of first wave and started living a normal life but the second wave has built a mental stress and anxiety. In second wave covid19 is spreading so fast that there is no vacancy for a bed in the hospital to treat a patient and less accessibility of oxygen and drugs and lack of treatment led to more mental stress and depression. Vaccination is playing a vital role in second wave of covid19 it led to a smaller number of covid cases and death rate.

Keywords: - Amazon, Trends, digital, online.

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/amierj/>

Introduction:

Amazon.com, Inc., an American Multinational Technology Company situated in Seattle, is a company involved in various businesses ranging from E-commerce, digital streaming, Artificial Intelligence, and cloud computing. Amazon comes under the top five US companies besides Apple, Microsoft, Facebook, and Google. with Google, Apple, Microsoft, and Facebook. Amazon is founded by Jeff Bezos, who founded the company in his garage on 5 July 1994. The company was started as a market for selling books, followed by software, video games, electronics, furniture, apparel, toys, jewellery, and food. Amazon is the world's biggest online marketplace. Many companies are founded under Amazon Music, Kindle, Fire TV, Fire Tablets, Prime Video, Amazon Studios, Whole Food Markets, IMDb, and Twitch.

There are Various New trends in Amazon Services: -

1. **Alexa shopping list** Amazon command Alexa to share the shopping list to the user. It is very useful for an individual to shortlist the shopping list they want to purchase.

The person who has difficulty in reading and writing Alexa help it out with her voice.

2. **Amazon Academy** help students to prepare for competitive entrance exams for JEE and NEET with the live mock test. Amazon Academy aims to bring high quality, affordable education to all, starting with those preparing for engineering entrance examinations. It is the free course for all the students.
3. **Amazon Business** Amazon Business helps to start-up with the business to the business owners and also helps to expand their business with the vast network of suppliers for easy ordering and bulk volume discounts. For members of Amazon Business Prime, additional deals and features are available to help manage their cash flow and control their business expenses. provides its users a purchasing solution for their registered business of any size. Each business can assign users who are allowed to go in and purchase business supplies on Amazon on behalf of their employers.
4. **Amazon family** provides Prime members the opportunity to avail exclusive family-oriented offers, age-based recommendations and discount coupons as part of their Prime benefits.
5. **Amazon Fresh** offers grocery items for sale, as well as members of such similar items from the main Amazon.com storefront. Items ordered through Amazon Fresh are available for home delivery on the same day or the next day, depending on the time of the order and the availability of delivery slots.
6. **Amazon Launchpad** provides you with business insights that will help you identify whitespaces, decide on product benefits and optimize your marketing mix. As part of Amazon Launchpad, you are eligible for: Access to a self-service Business Insights Suite: Comprising reports based on our market intelligence.
7. **Amazon pantry** Essentially, Amazon Pantry is an online store that allows Prime members and non-Prime members in select areas to buy non-perishable food items and household supplies in everyday package sizes. In other words, you won't have to buy the bulk sizes that you would find at Costco Wholesale or Sam's Club. Pantry allows Amazon to expand into the grocery and household supply sector, offering these items at cost-effective prices.
8. **Amazon Renewed** products is that which will be reused, recycle or repaired and tested to look and work like new. Repair/refurbish capability means that products must have electrical and/or mechanical components that can be replaced and/or upgraded to new or like-new condition.

9. **Amazon wallet** it is a gift or type of a loyalty card. You can easily scan the QR Code for the redemption of the points.
10. **Amazon Pay** provides the option to purchase goods and services from websites and mobile apps using the addresses and payment methods stored in the Amazon account, such as credit cards or a direct debit bank account or the unified payments interface in India.
11. **Amazon Coupon** Similar to the newspaper coupons you got in the mail growing up, Amazon Coupons are a way for customers to save money on products. When enabled on a product, Amazon Coupons appear as a button under the listing price of that product.
12. **Amazon prime** to avail the premium and priority services person can subscribe to the amazon prime and avail all the additional services.
13. **Amazon Alexa** Amazon Alexa, also known as Alexa, this technology is developed by Amazon, first used in the Amazon Echo smart speaker and the Echo dots. Alexa follows the order of alexa users.

Review of Literature

Ritala, Golnam, Wegmann (2014)

The researchers have mentioned in their study the advantages that can be gained through cooperation as a part of the company's business models. The researchers conducted a longitudinal and in deep research study on the models based on cooperation of the online portal, Amazon. The findings of the study revealed three distinct cooperation models, which are namely Amazon Services and Web Services, collaboration among Amazon and Apple on the digital text platform and Amazon Marketplace. The conclusions helped in deriving how can the value be created as well as captured through by including competitors in the business model.

Dokras (2017)

The Amazon Prime Pantry refers to the business of Amazon which is solely based on the sale of the basic household necessity products which includes water bottle or baby soap as such. This business undertaken by Amazon is a part and parcel of the consumable portfolio which has mostly exceeded or met the forecasting's done. Even though, the business flourishes as well as with that lower Average Sales Price (ASP) products are launched while fully optimizing present solution for fulfillment which is important for ensuring profitability with the help of growth.

Goyal, Mahajan (2020)

Online shopping has become the new and ongoing trend in the universe. There are large number of buyers increasing in India for online shopping and has become super compliance in analyzing the habit of purchasing among the digital purchasers as well in deriving useful conclusions. In the research study, it is being analyzed that if there is a stronger bond among the purchased product or product returned on Amazon portal and the type of the vendor. Also Amazon introduced the connection among count and category of the products purchased or either returned on the online portal. The shopping online has made a resemblance with the manner in which we shop through the catalogue, as in both the orders are received through mail service and also there is a lack of physical contact with the consumers.

Zhu, Liu (2018)

In the research study that the information is collected from Amazon.com has enabled the researchers in studying the pattern of entry in the third-party sellers' product arena and it is being seen that the online portal is evidently going to target the product spaces which are successful. It is also being seen that Amazon also wants to enter the spaces where the efforts of the seller is going to be much more on which the decision of investment is being made. But the entry of Amazon has impacted the third-party sellers entry into the constantly growing platform. It is being visible that the demand of the product is increasing as well as helps in reducing the cost of shipping for the customers.

Klaus (2013)

The research study focuses on analyzing and interpreting the concept of Online Customer Service Experience (OCSE) while selling products through the online portal. The research also focuses on the controllable variables which is experienced while purchasing online.

Objective

To study the awareness of various amazon services and strategies among the individuals of Mumbai region.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is a foundation upon which research is based. It is a beginning point of the research.it is a systematic plan to solve the problem.it is a logical plan to solve the problem.

Data Collection

The collection of data can be of two types, the first being the Primary data, and the second

being the secondary data.

Primary data: The primary data means the data collected directly from the sample respondents. The data will be used for analysis and interpretation.

The data can be collected from respondents by interview and structured questionnaire.

Secondary data: Secondary data means the data collected from readily available sources like books, articles, journals, magazines, etc.

In the current research work, both the primary and secondary data collection sources will be used for analysis purpose.

I have used the Survey Method in which I have collect the data from 60 respondent

- There are 21.7% respondent who are not aware of the new Amazon trends
- And there 78.3% who are aware of new amazon trends

- There is total 54.2% of amazon users from the total respondent
- And there are 45.8% of amazon users from the total respondent

Are you a Amazon prime member
60 responses

- There is 51.7% prime members from the total respondent
- There is 48.3% prime members from the total respondent

How much you are satisfied with Amazon Services in the scale of 1 to 5
60 responses

- From the scale of 1 to 5 the respondent who are not satisfied are 0% in the scale of 1
- Who are not fully satisfied on the scale of 5 is 3.3%

- So, there are many respondents who are satisfied as compare to not satisfied

Is Amazon shopping and Amazon deals benefial for you

60 responses

- There are 33.3% of respondent says yes, amazon shopping and amazon deals are beneficial to them
- There are 43.3% of respondents says No, amazon shopping and amazon deals are beneficial to them
- There are 23.3% of respondent who are not sure and says May be for, amazon shopping and amazon deals are beneficial to them

Are you aware of the exclusive family oriented offers of Amazon family

59 responses

- There are 67.8% respondent who are aware of the exclusive family oriented offers of Amazon family
- There are 32.2% respondent who are not aware of the exclusive family oriented offers of Amazon family

The Exclusive oriented offers of Amazon is beneficial for Family

60 responses

- There are 46.7% of respondent who are neutral about the exclusive oriented offers of amazon is beneficial for their family
- There are 35% of respondent who agree that exclusive oriented offers of amazon are beneficial for their family
- There are 10% of respondent who disagree that exclusive oriented offers of amazon are beneficial for their family
- There are 3% of respondent who strongly disagree that exclusive oriented offers of amazon are beneficial for their family
- There are 1.15% of respondent who strongly agree that exclusive oriented offers of amazon are beneficial for their family

Amazon fresh offers fresh products to the customers

60 responses

- There are 56.7% respondent who agrees that amazon fresh offers fresh products to the customers
- There are 30% respondent who disagree that amazon fresh offers fresh products to the customers
- There are 8.3% respondent who strongly disagree that amazon fresh offers fresh products to the customers
- There are 5% respondent who strongly agree that amazon fresh offers fresh products to the customers

Till what extent are you aware of Amazon Pay

60 responses

- There are 65% of respondent who are aware of amazon pay
- There are 26.7% of respondent who are not aware of amazon pay
- There are 8.3% of respondent who are not fully aware of amazon pay

Till what extent are you aware of Amazon Fresh
60 responses

- There are 51.7% respondent who are not aware of amazon fresh
- There are 16.7% respondent who are aware of amazon fresh
- There are 31.7% respondent who are not fully aware of amazon fresh

Does Amazon Pay make your purchase easy
60 responses

- There are 18.3% of respondent who says yes that amazon pay makes the purchase easy
- There are 58.3% of respondent who says No that amazon pay don't makes the purchase easy
- There are 23.3% of respondent who neither says yes or No are not sure that amazon pay makes the purchase easy or not

Does Amazon pay makes your financial statements secured

60 responses

- There are 33.3% of respondent who says yes that amazon pay makes the financial statements secure
- There are 66.7% of respondent who says No that amazon pay don't makes the financial statement secure

How is the service of Amazon prime to the customer

60 responses

-
- 63.3% of respondent are dissatisfied with the amazon prime service
 - 16.7% of respondent are satisfied with the amazon prime service
 - 13.3% of respondent are satisfied with the amazon prime service
 - 6.7% of respondent are highly dissatisfied with amazon prime sevice

Have you ever used the Amazon Alexa

60 responses

- There are 40% of respondent who have used Amazon alexa
- There are 80% of respondent who have not used Amazon alexa

Are you the part of Amazon Business Account

60 responses

- There are 38.3% respondent who are the part of amazon business account
- There are 61.7% respondent who are not the part of amazon business account

How are the products of the Amazon Fresh

60 responses

- There is 0% on scale of 1 for the product of amazon fresh
- There is 11.7% on the scale 2 for the product of amazon fresh
- There is 40% on the scale of 3 for the product of amazon fresh
- There is 40% on the scale of 4 for the product of amazon fresh
- There is 8.3% on the scale of 5 for the product of amazon fresh
- So, there is no a greater number of respondents who are satisfied with the product of amazon

Conclusion

The study says that in the updating digital world with upcoming new trends are also upgrading in which the best example is Amazon. Amazon is upgrading so fast from Amazon online shopping to so many new trends such as Amazon shopping, Amazon fresh, Amazon Pay, Amazon Business, Amazon family, Amazon Launchpad, Amazon Pantry, Amazon Academy, Amazon Alexa, Amazon Prime Videos and etc. The Amazon has made the human life so easy one can watch the movies and entrained listen to unlimited music ,one can do unlimited shopping with infinite product options and yes with financial security, one can pay there bills with help of amazon pay so easily , one can start with there own business with very less capital with the help of amazon business, etc and this way the new trends of Amazon is making aware of this digital world and new

trends .In the survey the study says that there are many individual who are not aware of the new trends of amazon and there are many individual who are not satisfied using Amazon services and there are many Individual who are very much satisfied with the amazon and now they are a regular users.

References

1. P. Ritala, A. Golnam, A. Wegmann (2014). Coopetition-based business models: The case of Amazon.com. *Industrial Marketing Management*. Volume- 43, Issue- 2, P. 236-249.
2. Dokras, v. (2017). Prime Pantry Optimization: A Cost Analysis and Deep-Dive in Process Improvement. *Massachusetts Institute of Technology Publishers*. Issue- 5, P. 1-68.
3. Goyal, M. Mahajan, Y. (2020). Review of buy orders and return from Amazon.in in India: Implications for Amazon and its vendors. *Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology*. Volume- 7, Issue- 6, P. 786-799.
4. Zhu, F. Liu, Q. (2018). Competing with complementors: An empirical look at Amazon.com. *Strategic Management Journal*. Volume- 39, Issue- 10, P. 2618-2642.
5. Klaus, P. (2013). The case of Amazon.com: towards a conceptual framework of online customer service experience (OCSE) using the emerging consensus technique (ECT). *Journal of Services Marketing*. Volume-27, Issue- 6.